

Employee Welfare in Manufacturing–Industry Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Employee welfare means anything done for the comfort and improvement of the employee. The Employers offer an extra incentive in from of employee welfare is to enrich the life of employee and keep them happy. The working environment in a factory adversely affects the working health. In some of the factory may lead to the employee health condition worst so the work of employee may get into trouble and the health problems will be there so that the welfare measures should be given for their health and the life. The factors of the welfare are safety helmet at the workplace, first aid box for the emergency in case of any injuries to the employee while doing the work, most wanted in our daily life is food and water so that should be provided, in case the employee at different place come and work for them shelter should be given, some employees may suffer from the ventilation so the factory should have that facility. In this paper we are going see whether the employee gets their welfare correctly and whether they are satisfied with their need and wants if not we will suggest them with some ideas.

KEYWORDS: Employee welfare, satisfaction, facility, statutory, non statutory

INTRODUCTION

An employee welfare activity in India was large Influenced by the humanitarian approach. The economic development of a country depends upon the production of commodities and services after the employee gave been hired, trained and remunerated they need to be retained and maintained for overall growth of an organization. welfare facilities gave been mainly development to look after the wellbeing of an employee which ultimately leads to physical mental and moral health of an employee.

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HUMAN RESOURCE:

Human Resource Management (HRM) is concerned with the “people” dimension in management. Since every organization is made up of people, developing skills, motivating them to higher level of performance, and

ensuring that they continue to maintain their commitment to the organization are essential to achieving organization objectives.

EMPLOYEE WELFARE:

The term employee welfare is a broad term which comprises of numerous services, facilities and benefit that the employee offers to the employee. In includes job, comfort, contentment, protection and growth of human capital. It help employee to set minimum desirable standards like housing, health, clothing, education, job, insurance and fun for themselves. Such incentives enable the workers to live a satisfaction social and work life. Employee welfare booster the morale of employee and motivates them to such an extent that they to not leave the organization for long time The measure taken for employees welfare can be both cash or kind.

CLASSIFICATION OF EMPLOYEE WELFARE:

STATUTORY WELFARE:

Statutory refers to something that is related to a formal law or a statute. Statutory bodies are established by acts which parliament and state legislatures can pass. Theses bodies are entities shaped by an Act of parliament or state legislatures and set up by the Government to consider the data and make judgments in some in some area of activity.

➤ Drinking water facility:

This is why drinking water also contains minimal amounts of chlorine. Water mostly consists of minerals and other inorganic compounds, such as calcium

How to cite this paper: Dr. M. Robinson | S. Chitra "Employee Welfare in Manufacturing–Industry Literature Review" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-4 | Issue-2, February 2020, pp.1107-1109, URL: www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd30173.pdf

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➤ **Facility for sitting:**

Facility sitting is an assessment of occupied buildings given potential exposure to explosion, fire and toxic hazards. As stated in the Occupational Safety and Health Administration

➤ **First aid box:**

First aid kits are designed to manage all types of injuries including basic cuts, scrapes and burns. Save yourself money and keep a stocked first aid kit close by. Accidents are unexpected - Being prepared can reduce panic and provide the necessary aid.

➤ **Lighting:**

Lighting includes the use of both artificial light sources like lamps and light fixtures, as well as natural illumination by capturing daylight. Day lighting (using windows, skylights, or light shelves) is sometimes used as the main source of light during daytime in buildings.

➤ **Canteen Facility:**

The definition of a canteen is a place where food is provided in a military camp, college or other organization, or a small container for holding drinking liquids. A cafeteria in college where all the kids go to eat is an example of a canteen.

➤ **Latrines and urinal:**

A latrine is a toilet or an even simpler facility which is used as a toilet within a sanitation system. For example, it can be a communal trench in the earth in a camp to be used as emergency sanitation, a hole in the ground (pit latrine), or more advanced designs, including pour-flush systems.

NON STATUTORY:

Non – statutory is essentially another term for common law. Therefore such bodies are formed by executive resolution or action, which means that they are formed only by the government's action.

➤ **Personal Health Care**

Refers to the wellness of the individual. While personal health care is provided to people those who are not able to take care of themselves. Personal health is the ability to take charge of your health by making conscious decisions to be healthy.

➤ **Flexi-time:**

Short for flexible time, is a work arrangement that allows employees to choose their workday's starting and finishing time. As employees seek a better balance between work and home, flex time offers an opportunity to better manage time.

➤ **Employee Assistance Programs**

Employee assistance program (EAP) is an employee benefit program that assists employees with personal problems and/or work-related problems that may impact their job performance, health, mental and emotional well-being EAPs have grown in popularity over the years, and are more desirable economically and socially.

➤ **Employee Referral Scheme:**

Definition, employee referral is a structured program that companies and organizations use to find talented people by asking their existing employees

➤ **Harassment Policy:**

Employee policies and procedures are descriptions of how all employees, regardless of job description or title, are expected to conduct themselves. Employee policies and procedures are typically developed by a company's human resources (hr) department and distributed to all employees

EMPLOYEE WELFARE FUND:

A Fund usually Majority of employee in India working an un organization sector. In order to provide social security to such workers, Government has introduced employee welfare fund to ensure assistance to unorganized employee.

1. Housing:

Housing, or more generally living spaces, refers to the construction and assigned usage of houses or buildings collectively, for the purpose of sheltering people — the planning or provision delivered by an authority

2. Recreational:

facility, installation - a building or place that provides a particular service or is used for a particular industry; "the assembly plant is an enormous facility" lido -a recreational facility. Social Security

3. Educational:

Educational facilities include buildings, fixtures, and equipment necessary for the effective and efficient operation of the program of public education, classrooms, libraries, rooms and space for physical education, space for fine arts, restrooms, specialized laboratories, cafeterias, media centers, building equipment.

4. Transportation:

Many employers provide commuter benefits to soften the blow of the high cost of commuting and to help recruit and/or retain valuable employees. This voluntary employee benefit program allows employees to reduce their monthly commuting expenses related to parking, transit, vanpooling and bicycling.

Medical Facility:

Before discussing the broad provisions, we should keep in mind the following points –

1. Fixed medical allowance is always chargeable to tax.
2. For the purpose of valuation of the perquisite in respect of medical facilities, "family.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

PATRO, CHANDRA SEKHAR(2017)study in employee welfare Employee plays an important role in the industrial production of the company. Hence, the organization should give cooperation to the employees in order to increase the production and to earn higher profits. Employee benefit constitute a major vehicle for the provision of income and security.

MANASA, B. R., AND C.N. KRISHN ANAIK. (2015)"Employee welfare measures-A study on cement corporation. the analysis of their study concept of employee welfare. the study resultant that employee's in auto sector are highly satisfied with the intra-mural welfare measure. welfare facilities provided to customer. By the study suggestion are made that it may be railway minimize the cost of social burden and apply for government for betterment of Employee welfare.

RAMANA, T. VENKATA, AND E. LOKANADHA REDDY. (2015). "A study on employee welfare refer to they want to assess the overall satisfaction level regarding welfare program. Through their papers they want to obtain correction By the study suggestion are made that it may be railway minimize the cost of social burden and apply for government for betterment of welfare provisions .between statutory and non-statutory activities at industry and to obtain relationship between employees.

LALITHA, K., AND T. PRIYANKA..(2014)" welfare facilities provided at the company (Bosch limited Bangalore). The study discusses extend of awareness among the employee's with various statutory and no statutory welfare measure. It is found that most of the welfare facilities like medical canteen, working environment safety measure etc. are provide by company and most of the employee's are satisfied with the welfare facilities.

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VENUGOPAL, D.,(2011) A study on employee welfare any relation exists between welfare provisions and employee's satisfaction. His study also reviews on welfare provisions and employee's satisfaction. from their study they concluded that voluntary welfare measure should be provided to employee. They study the level of awareness of employee about the various welfare measures.

SABARIRAJAN, A., T. MEHARAJAN, AND B.(2010) "A study on the various welfare measures and their impact on QWL provided by the Textile Mills with reference to Salem District. the statutory welfare measure provided by

employees. They study analysis and interpret about the statutory welfare measures in the proposed sample unit. It stated the employee's welfare is a comprehensive term including various services offered to employees of the organization.

CONCLUSION:

The study of employee welfare is observed that the organization provides various facilities to the employees. The management required to provide good facilities to satisfy the employees. It enhances the productivity as well as satisfaction.

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